
PROPOSED SUSTAINABLE HUB FOR THE GAINZA PUBLIC MARKET

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Abstract

This study examined how the operational conditions of the Gainza Public Market covering its physical infrastructure, management systems, accessibility, inclusiveness, and procurement mechanisms affected its overall sustainability across economic, social, and environmental dimensions, aligning with SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). Using a mixed-methods approach anchored in the frameworks of Inclusive Local Economic Development, Community Co-Production, Sustainable Development Governance, and Urban Sustainability and Circular Economy, the study integrated quantitative surveys from consumers, vendors, and market users with qualitative insights from open-ended responses and FGDs involving LGU officials and stakeholders. Descriptive statistics, weighted means, and thematic analysis were applied to primary data. Findings showed generally neutral stakeholder perceptions of accessibility, activation readiness, and procurement inclusion, with Average Weighted Means between 3.18 and 3.72, suggesting operational functionality but limited optimization. Key challenges identified included the market's location, limited transportation access, incomplete facilities, water and sanitation concerns, and institutional management gaps. Analytical results indicated a clear association between operational conditions and sustainability outcomes, emphasizing how infrastructure quality, governance practices, and service mechanisms shape economic viability and community participation. Qualitative insights further highlighted the need for coordinated physical improvements, stronger governance structures, digital integration, and greater community involvement. Overall, the study concludes that comprehensive interventions in infrastructure upgrading, institutional reforms, inclusive procurement, and stakeholder activation are essential to position the Gainza Public Market as a sustainable and participatory local economic hub

Keywords: *Public market sustainability, operational conditions, local economic development, governance, infrastructure improvement.*

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INTRODUCTION

Public markets had long served as important economic and social institutions around the world. Globally, they functioned as primary center of exchange, providing livelihood opportunities for small entrepreneurs, ensuring food security, and fostering cultural interaction within communities. Throughout history, public markets evolved into dynamic spaces that supported inclusive economies and sustainable urban development. However, with the onset of globalization, modernization, and digitalization, many traditional markets faced operational decline. Studies in Europe and the Americas showed that global market systems struggled with competition from supermarkets, online commerce, and large retail chains (Borucka et al., 2022). In response, various cities began implementing sustainable market revitalization programs that integrated environmental design, community participation, and digital innovations to preserve the social and economic significance of traditional markets.

In Asia, public markets remained vital components of local economies, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas. They provided essential trading spaces for farmers, fisher folks and micro-entrepreneurs. Asian countries such as Vietnam, Indonesia, and Thailand successfully revitalized their traditional markets by adopting sustainable infrastructure and governance frameworks that emphasized community participation, green architecture, and local economic inclusion (UNDP Vietnam, 2024; Pratama & Santosa, 2020). These initiatives demonstrated that sustainable public market development could strengthen rural–urban linkages, stimulate tourism, and advance several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities).

In the Philippines, public markets had historically served as the economic heart of municipalities, where small-scale traders, farmers, and consumers converged. Since the Spanish colonial period, they had been the focal point of local trade and food distribution. However, in recent decades, several Philippine public markets faced issues of deterioration, mismanagement, and declining patronage due to poor infrastructure, lack of modernization, and inadequate policy support from local government units (LGUs) (De Guzman, 2023). To address these challenges, national and local governments began integrating sustainability principles into market planning, guided by the Philippine Development Plan (2023–2028) and the United Nations SDGs, promoting infrastructure resilience, economic inclusivity, and environmental responsibility (Balbacal, 2021).

In the municipality of Gainza, Camarines Sur, this issue became particularly evident. Despite being separated from Naga City since 1863, Gainza remained dependent on neighboring towns for market access for over a century. In 2024, the LGU constructed its first municipal public market to strengthen local commerce and provide livelihood opportunities. However, after only a few months of operation, the market ceased functioning due to various factors, including lack of customers, few vendors, inadequate facilities, limited accessibility, and the absence of clear operational policies and management systems. The closure led to reduced economic activities, loss of income for vendors, and financial strain on the LGU.

Given these challenges, the need to redevelop the Gainza Public Market as a sustainable hub became necessary. This study was therefore conducted to assess its sustainability through policy and community dimensions and to propose implementation guidelines for its redevelopment. Anchored on the Sustainable Development Theory, Triple Bottom Line Theory, Institutional Theory, and Community Participation Theory, the study aimed to formulate a holistic model that would integrate inclusive governance, sustainability practices, and stakeholder engagement to restore the market’s role as a catalyst for local economic growth.

The study was intended to benefit various sectors by providing data-driven insights that strengthened the sustainable management of the Gainza Public Market. The LGU of Gainza was supported through evidence-based guidelines that improved governance, policymaking, and administrative efficiency. Market vendors gained from recommendations that addressed operational issues, improved infrastructure, and promoted fair, stable business conditions. Consumers and residents benefited from proposed improvements that enhanced safety, accessibility, and the overall market environment. The local business sector was guided toward increased economic opportunities and stronger entrepreneurial activity. National government agencies such as DTI, DA, and DILG were provided with localized evidence that supported the enforcement of standards and inter-agency coordination. Community organizations were empowered through participatory approaches incorporated in the study. Academicians and researchers gained new empirical insights on rural public market sustainability, while future policymakers and planners were equipped with frameworks and tools applicable to broader development initiatives.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to assess the sustainability of the Gainza Public Market in Camarines Sur through policy and community dimensions. Specifically, it addressed the following:

1. To assess the status for possible full operation of the Gainza Public Market in terms of (a) physical infrastructure (b) management and (c) economics and business activities;
2. To assess the prospects for possible full operation of the Gainza Public Market in terms of (a) economic growth potential (b) environmental sustainability and (c) policy and institutional readiness;
3. To assess the level of sustainability of Gainza Public Market in terms of (a) economic performance (b) social inclusiveness and (c) environmental management; and
4. To develop Implementation guidelines for Gainza Public Market as a sustainable hub in Camarines Sur.

Scope and Delimitations

This study assessed the sustainability of the Gainza Public Market by examining its physical, operational, economic, social, environmental, and institutional conditions within the locality of Gainza, Camarines Sur. The scope of the research was limited to stakeholders residing or operating within Gainza, specifically consumers living in the municipality, current market vendors, and local government officials directly involved in market administration. The investigation focused solely on the municipal public market located in Gainza, evaluating its governance systems, facilities, and daily operational practices. Conducted during the School Year 2025–2026, the study aimed to support the development of Implementation Guidelines for establishing a sustainable market hub; however, it did not include the creation of architectural plans, engineering designs, or budget programming beyond existing LGU data.

The study was delimited to aspects related only to the operations and management of the Gainza Public Market, excluding factors outside the direct scope of public market sustainability. Markets located outside the municipality of Gainza, including private and commercial establishments, were not included, as their operational structures differ from LGU-managed public markets. The study did not cover broader areas such as consumer behavior analysis, pricing elasticity, or marketing strategies, since these were beyond the central focus on sustainability and governance. The research was intentionally limited to the Gainza Public Market to ensure depth, feasibility, and contextual relevance within the given timeframe. Despite

limitations arising from time constraints, restricted access to some official records, and reliance on stakeholder self-reports, the study-maintained reliability through triangulation, validation sessions, and expert review.

Theoretical Framework

The sustainable redevelopment of the Gainza Public Market was anchored on four contemporary theoretical perspectives: Sustainable Development Governance Theory (Meadowcroft, 2017), Inclusive Local Economic Development Theory (Sotarauta & Beer, 2020), Community Co-Production Theory (Verschuere et al., 2018), and Urban Sustainability and Circular Economy Theory (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). Together, these theories provide a multidimensional analytical foundation for examining the market's policy, community, economic, and environmental dimensions.

Sustainable Development Governance Theory by Meadowcroft (2017) emphasizes that achieving sustainability depends on the effectiveness of institutions and the coherence of policies that guide local development initiatives. The author argues that governance for sustainability requires the integration of environmental, economic, and social priorities into decision-making and implementation processes. This includes transparent governance systems, participatory mechanisms, and alignment with broader development agendas such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In the context of the Gainza Public Market, this theory explains how local government units (LGUs) influence the market's sustainability through policy formulation, regulatory enforcement, infrastructure planning, and stakeholder coordination. The theory underpins the study's examination of the institutional and policy dimensions that shape the market's operational viability and long-term redevelopment.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Theoretical framework illustrating the integration of Sustainable Development Governance, Inclusive Local Economic Development, Community Co-Production, Urban Sustainability and Circular Economy theories in assessing the sustainability of the Gainza Public Market.

Inclusive Local Economic Development (LED) Theory by Sotarauta & Beer (2020) provides the economic foundation for the study. They argue that inclusive LED occurs when economic growth strategies intentionally involve marginalized groups, small entrepreneurs, and local communities in economic activities. This theory highlights the importance of creating supportive environments for microenterprises, strengthening rural–urban linkages, and promoting equitable economic opportunities. Applied to the Gainza Public Market, the theory informs the assessment of economic growth potential, market viability, and livelihood opportunities for vendors, farmers, and micro-entrepreneurs. It supports the study’s focus on economic sustainability by recognizing public markets as critical nodes for local trade, income generation, and community-based commerce.

Community Co-Production Theory by Verschuere et al. (2018) posits that public services and community facilities become more effective and sustainable when they are co-designed, co-implemented, and co-managed by both government and citizens. According to Verschuere, Brandsen, and Pestoff (2018), co-production fosters community ownership, enhances service quality, and strengthens institutional responsiveness. For the Gainza Public Market, this theory underscores the importance of engaging stakeholders—such as vendors, consumers, cooperatives, and community groups—in the development and operation of the market. Co-production is particularly relevant in addressing challenges related to vendor participation, market management, and community utilization. The theory supports the study’s community dimension by emphasizing collaborative governance as a pathway to sustainability.

Urban Sustainability and Circular Economy Theory by Geissdoerfer et al. (2017) provides the environmental basis for the study. They conceptualize the circular economy as a regenerative model that minimizes waste, extends material lifespan, and promotes resource efficiency. In urban contexts, circular economy principles support environmentally sustainable urban development through practices such as waste segregation, recycling, composting, renewable energy use, and green infrastructure integration. This theory guides the environmental assessment of the Gainza Public Market by offering criteria for evaluating ecological performance and the potential integration of sustainable design elements. It also informs the development of guidelines aimed at reducing environmental impact and enhancing operational efficiency through circular practices.

The convergence of these four theories formed the conceptual foundation of the study. The theoretical integration asserted that sustainable redevelopment of the Gainza Public Market can be achieved when effective governance enables inclusive local economic participation, strengthened through community co-production, and supported by circular economy–based environmental practices. This integrated perspective recognizes sustainability as a multidimensional construct influenced by policymaking, economic empowerment, community collaboration, and environmental stewardship. It provided the necessary framework for assessing the market’s current condition, identifying prospects for redevelopment, and formulating implementation guidelines for its transformation into a sustainable hub.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the Proposed Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market was anchored on the Input–Process–Output (IPO) model, which illustrates how existing market conditions are systematically evaluated to generate evidence-based sustainability outcomes and operational guidelines. The framework begun with assessing the current operations of the municipal market—its physical structure, management systems, and economic activities—which serve as the foundational inputs. These inputs entered a multidimensional analytical

process focused on examining market operations, sustainability levels, and institutional readiness. Through this mechanism, the study evaluates economic growth potential, environmental performance, social inclusiveness, and governance efficiency. The process resulted in measurable outputs, including a comprehensive status report on market readiness, documentation of growth and sustainability potential, and a sustainability rating across key dimensions. These outputs then inform the development of Implementation Guidelines for the Sustainable Operations and Development of the Gainza Public Market, which provided strategic directions for transforming the existing public market into a fully functional sustainable hub.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework showing the interaction of inputs, processes, and outputs in assessing and developing the Gainza Public Market into a sustainable hub.

In Figure 2, the inputs consist of the existing conditions of the Gainza Public Market, which include its current market operations, encompassing physical infrastructure, management practices, and economic and business activities. These elements provided the necessary baseline information to understand how the market is currently functioning and where critical gaps lie. The physical infrastructure included the layout, facilities, sanitation systems, and structural conditions of the market. Management practices involve administrative procedures, regulatory enforcement, stall allocation, vendor relations, and financial management. Meanwhile, economic and business activities refer to vendor operations, product diversity, pricing systems, consumer flow, and revenue-generating mechanisms. Together, these inputs offer a comprehensive picture of the operational environment that must be assessed to determine the market's sustainability potential.

The process stage included two major analytical components: Market Operations Assessment and Level of Sustainability Analysis. Market operations assessment evaluates the economic growth potentials, environmental sustainability, and policy and institutional readiness of the Gainza Public Market. This process identified strengths, operational inefficiencies, environmental risks, administrative challenges, and regulatory alignment with LGU and national policies. The second component, sustainability analysis, measures the degree of economic performance (market income, vendor livelihood stability, business viability), social inclusiveness (vendor participation, accessibility, health and safety compliance), and environmental management (waste disposal, water use efficiency, sanitation systems, climate resilience). This dual-layer evaluation ensured that both operational and sustainability indicators are considered, allowing for a holistic understanding of the market's long-term viability.

The outputs of the analysis produced three major results that serve as the foundation for strategic improvements in the Gainza Public Market. First, a Status Report on Market Readiness was generated to present the overall condition of the market, particularly its infrastructure, management practices, and regulatory systems. Second, a comprehensive Report on Economic Growth Potential, Sustainability, and Institutional Support synthesized the market's capacity to enhance local livelihoods, strengthen environmental performance, and improve governance mechanisms. Third, a Sustainability Rating across economic, social, and environmental dimensions provided a measurable assessment of the market's long-term viability and readiness for sustainable development. Together, these outputs create a data-driven basis for designing targeted interventions and implementing development strategies that support the establishment of a sustainable market hub in Gainza.

Based on the outputs of the assessment, the study proposed Implementation Guidelines aimed at transforming the Gainza Public Market into a sustainable community hub. These guidelines included strengthening institutional governance through clearer policies and transparent administrative systems; improving physical infrastructure by integrating green and climate-resilient features; enhancing market operations through vendor support, sanitation improvement, and waste management reforms; and promoting social inclusiveness by ensuring equitable stall distribution, community participation, and public safety. Environmental guidelines emphasized circular economy practices such as waste segregation, composting initiatives, and the adoption of energy-efficient technologies. Economic guidelines focused on improving business viability through capacity-building programs, fair rental systems, and revenue management improvements. Altogether, the guidelines provided a strategic roadmap that enables the Gainza LGU to implement sustainable, community-centered market development anchored in evidence and long-term resilience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sustainability of Public Markets

The sustainability of public markets has emerged as a critical area of study as communities increasingly rely on these local economic hubs for livelihood generation, food accessibility, and social cohesion. Public markets are not merely commercial spaces but multifunctional community assets whose long-term viability depends on the balance of economic performance, social inclusiveness, and environmental responsibility. As cities and municipalities confront challenges such as urbanization, shifting consumer behavior, climate impacts, and resource limitations, the need to ensure that public markets operate sustainably has become more urgent. Contemporary literature highlights those sustainable markets contribute to resilient local economies, strengthen community engagement, reduce environmental footprints, and support circular economic practices. Within this context, examining the sustainability of public markets provides valuable insights into how these infrastructures can be enhanced or redeveloped to remain functional, competitive, and socially relevant, particularly in rural and developing municipalities such as Gainza.

Sustainable Development Theory provided the overarching lens through which public market sustainability is understood, emphasizing the integration of economic viability, environmental protection, and social equity. Applying this theory to public markets underscores the importance of planning, regulation, and stakeholder collaboration in achieving long-term

sustainability, particularly in rural communities seeking to enhance market functionality and community welfare.

Circular economy approaches have transformed the way public markets are conceptualized by encouraging systems that minimize waste, maximize resource efficiency, and promote regenerative practices. In the context of public markets, this framework supported sustainable operations through practices such as waste segregation, composting, upcycling of organic waste, and energy-efficient design. Circular principles also align with low-carbon development strategies, making them especially relevant in the redesign or redevelopment of community markets aiming to reduce environmental impacts while supporting local economic activity.

Sustainable urban market development has been widely promoted by organizations such as UN-Habitat and the FAO, which advocate for market systems that are inclusive, resilient, and environmentally responsible. These agencies emphasized the role of well-managed markets in strengthening urban food security, supporting microenterprises, and enhancing community well-being. UN-Habitat's frameworks highlight accessibility, safety, and multifunctionality as core dimensions of sustainable market design, while FAO publications stress the need for adequate infrastructure, sanitation, energy-efficient systems, and vendor support programs. Together, these perspectives reinforce the importance of adopting integrated sustainability approaches to ensure that public markets can adapt to urban pressures while remaining vital community assets.

Local markets serve as critical nodes in community food systems, enabling the distribution of fresh, affordable, and culturally relevant food while supporting local producers. FAO studies (2019–2024) emphasize that resilient food systems depend on efficient local markets that ensure stable supply chains, reduce food loss, and enhance access to nutritious products. These studies highlight the importance of strengthening rural–urban linkages, supporting small-scale farmers, and building market infrastructures that can withstand economic, climatic, and logistical shocks. Through this lens, sustainable public markets contribute significantly to food system resilience by fostering local production, enhancing food security, and supporting livelihoods within communities.

Community participation is essential in the sustainable development and governance of public markets, as it fosters shared ownership, collaborative decision-making, and improved service delivery. In public markets, co-production encourages vendor involvement, stakeholder engagement, and community consultation in planning and operational decisions. This collaborative process enhances market relevance, supports transparent governance, and ensures that redevelopment efforts align with local needs and aspirations, ultimately contributing to more sustainable and accepted public spaces.

Sustainability assessment tools, including those based on the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework, offer structured methods for evaluating the economic, environmental, and social performance of public markets. TBL literature highlights that sustainable development must balance these three pillars to ensure long-term viability and equitable outcomes. Indicators commonly include economic productivity, environmental efficiency, social equity, vendor satisfaction, governance quality, and resource utilization. These tools assist policymakers and market administrators in identifying gaps, prioritizing interventions, and monitoring improvement over time. Applying such assessment frameworks enables evidence-based decision-making and supports the development of more sustainable and resilient market operations.

Traditional markets in Asia have been the focus of revitalization efforts led by organizations such as UNDP and ASEAN, which recognize their importance in cultural preservation, local economic development, and community resilience. Studies highlight challenges faced by Asian markets, including competition from supermarkets, outdated infrastructure, and inadequate governance systems. Revitalization programs emphasize modernization, enhanced sanitation, improved vendor support, and the integration of digital tools while preserving cultural identity. These efforts demonstrate that sustainable development of traditional markets requires a balance between modernization and cultural continuity, ensuring that markets remain competitive, vibrant, and relevant in the evolving urban landscape.

In the research on how Local Government Units (LGUs) manage public markets provides a strong foundation for analyzing sustainable market operations. Isolana (2021), in his study *Public-Private Partnership (PPP) as an Alternative Model to Public Infrastructure Development and Service Delivery*, examined PPP-managed public markets in the Philippines and found that while private operators improved infrastructure and services early on, these improvements declined when control returned to LGUs. These studies are relevant to the Gainza Public Market hub because they show that infrastructure improvements alone are insufficient; sustainability depends on strong institutional arrangements, clear governance systems, and long-term operational capacities of the LGU—factors central to creating a “sustainable hub” model for Gainza.

Research on vendor regulation reveals the challenges vendors face under complex or inconsistent regulatory systems. Solidum (2023), in her study on the *Status and Problems of Street Vendors*, found that unclear policies, irregular enforcement, and limited LGU support reduce vendor compliance and livelihood stability. Peimani et al. (2022), through a systematic review of informal street vending, emphasized that poorly designed permitting systems often exclude marginalized vendors and create enforcement conflict. These findings directly relate to the Gainza Public Market, as they demonstrate the need for a fair, transparent, and inclusive permitting/licensing framework in the market hub—one that supports vendors’ livelihoods while standardizing safety, sanitation, and accountability practices.

Studies on market operations consistently show that small vendors face multiple constraints in capital, storage, pricing strategies, and customer management. Abitria (2024), in her empirical study of night market vendors in Albay, identified key operational challenges such as limited start-up capital, inadequate storage facilities, competition, and regulatory burdens. For the Gainza Public Market hub, these studies highlight the need to integrate vendor-supportive operational features—such as proper stall design, storage, waste facilities, and fair rental systems—to strengthen revenue stability and operational sustainability.

Comparative assessments between public and private market systems emphasize trade-offs between efficiency, equity, and regulatory control. Isolana (2021) found that PPP-managed markets often show early improvements but risk inequity when profit motives overshadow public service goals. These comparative insights are relevant to the Gainza hub because they indicate that a hybrid or balanced management model—combining public oversight with operational efficiency—is preferable for ensuring inclusiveness, fairness, and sustainability. The hub must avoid over-commercialization and instead maintain affordability, accessibility, and equity for all market users.

Studies evaluating transparency in local governance underscore the importance of efficient systems in delivering public services. Tan and Flor (2022), in their study of LGU efficiency in the Philippines, found that transparency mechanisms, digitalization, and institutional

capacity strongly influence service quality, including business registration and licensing. These findings are highly relevant to the Gainza Public Market hub because the project's sustainability depends on accountable LGU procedures, transparent financial management, and clear administrative processes to ensure fair stall allocation, revenue management, and regular maintenance.

Accessibility studies highlight the role of markets as essential public service spaces. Armas et al. (2024) developed a strategic framework for ambulant vendors in the Philippines and emphasized that accessibility, sanitation, and health compliance improve market functionality and community welfare. For the Gainza Public Market hub, these studies underscore the importance of designing the market as an accessible, hygienic, and community-centered space—ensuring that both consumers and vendors benefit from improved services, safer infrastructure, and equitable access.

Perception studies reveal how stakeholders interpret legality, fairness, and governance within local markets. Kirumirah et al. (2024) found that vendors' perceptions of their legal status influence their willingness to comply with regulations and participate in formal market systems. Romero et al. (2024), in their action research on Manila street vendors, showed that negative experiences with enforcement and policy exclusion reduce cooperation and trust in LGUs. These insights directly inform the Gainza Public Market hub, suggesting that stakeholder engagement—especially vendor consultation—must be central to planning and governance. Incorporating vendor perceptions fosters trust, reduces conflict, and improves long-term compliance.

Research on inter-agency collaboration highlights the need for clearly defined institutional roles in public service delivery. This is relevant to the Gainza Public Market hub since market governance typically involves joint responsibilities from DTI (consumer protection), DA (agriculture/food supply), DOH (sanitation), and the LGU (operations and regulation). Effective coordination ensures consistent policies, efficient inspection systems, and integrated market development.

Case studies of failed or struggling market redevelopment efforts offer lessons for sustainable planning. Isolana (2021) documented how PPP market reforms eventually deteriorated when LGUs lacked capacity to maintain improvements—leading to sanitation problems, conflict over stall allocation, and vendor dissatisfaction. These patterns mirror challenges seen in many Philippine markets that underwent redevelopment without long-term governance plans. For the Gainza Public Market hub, these lessons stress the importance of sustainability planning, preventive maintenance, vendor participation, continuous LGU oversight, and mechanisms to avoid reverting to pre-reform problems.

Studies on ICT in public governance demonstrate how digitalization can modernize market management. Tan and Taeihagh (2020), in their systematic review of smart governance in developing countries, found that technologies such as e-permitting, digital monitoring, and real-time data systems improve efficiency but only succeed when accompanied by institutional readiness and inclusivity. This is relevant to the Gainza Public Market hub because integrating digital tools—such as electronic vendor registration, digital stall allocation, or mobile-based compliance monitoring—can enhance transparency and reduce operational burdens. However, the hub must ensure digital inclusivity so that small or informal vendors are not left behind.

Governance and Operational Management of Public Markets

Effective governance and operational management were essential components in ensuring the efficiency, sustainability, and long-term viability of public markets, particularly in developing local economies where these facilities serve as central hubs of commerce and community interaction. Public markets require clear regulatory frameworks, transparent management systems, and active participation from vendors, consumers, and local government units (LGUs) to function optimally. Contemporary literature emphasizes that well-governed markets are characterized by structured stall allocation, consistent enforcement of sanitation and safety regulations, sound financial management, and mechanisms that foster collaboration between stakeholders. As challenges such as mismanagement, poor infrastructure maintenance, low vendor participation, and weak institutional capacity persist in many local markets, especially in rural municipalities, understanding governance and operational models becomes increasingly important. This topic explores the various administrative approaches, policy interventions, and institutional arrangements that influence the successful operation of public markets, offering critical insight for restructuring underperforming markets like the Gainza Public Market.

Sotarauta and Beer (2020) emphasized that Inclusive Local Economic Development (LED) requires engaging multiple local actors, fostering equitable participation, and building institutional capacities that support sustainable local markets. Their theory highlights how local development must be people-centered, ensuring that vulnerable groups, including small vendors, benefit from economic initiatives. This literature is highly relevant to the development of a Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because it affirms that local markets are not merely economic spaces but important community development arenas where inclusiveness, vendor empowerment, and community-centered governance must guide policy and design decisions.

Literature on public market governance stressed that markets operated by local governments require clear legal frameworks, consistent enforcement, and equitable policy implementation to function effectively. Studies on LGU governance highlight those public markets often suffer from outdated ordinances, unclear operating procedures, and weak monitoring systems, which impede efficiency and sustainability. This is directly relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because strengthening governance—through updated policies on stall allocation, sanitation, transparency, and vendor rights—will serve as the foundation for creating a more organized and resilient market system.

Institutional theory explained how rules, norms, and organizational structures shape the behavior of market actors and influence the long-term viability of economic spaces. Scholars argue that effective institutions enable predictable, fair, and coordinated market operations, while weak or inconsistent rules result in inefficiencies and informal practices. Applying this lens is relevant to the development of the Gainza Public Market hub because institutionalizing processes, such as vendor permitting, rental systems, and sanitation standards, ensures consistency, reduces conflict, and promotes a sustainable market environment aligned with national and local policy frameworks.

Public administration literature stressed the importance of efficiency, transparency, and accountability in delivering public services, including market management. Classic and contemporary authors emphasize that LGUs must employ systems that reduce bureaucracy, streamline operations, and optimize resource use. Improving administrative efficiency in public markets leads to better revenue collection, clearer vendor documentation, and faster service delivery. This is crucial for the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because inefficient administrative processes often cause crowding, poor sanitation, unclear vendor roles, and financial leakages, issues that a well-managed market hub seeks to resolve.

Study shows that involving community members, such as vendors, customers, and local associations, improves compliance, increases ownership, and strengthens service quality. This literature is directly relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because the market's long-term success depends on active community participation in maintaining cleanliness, promoting safety, reporting issues, and shaping policies. Co-production ensures that reforms are accepted, practiced, and sustained by the very people who use the market daily.

Studies on market regulation emphasized that effective LGU systems must balance control, fairness, and livelihood protection. Regulatory literature shows that clear guidelines on stall allocation, pricing, sanitation, and zoning help prevent disorder, promote safety, and ensure equitable operation. In many developing regions, weak enforcement leads to congestion, illegal vending, and health risks. This perspective is relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because establishing well-defined, consistently enforced regulations will minimize operational problems and support a more orderly, safe, and sustainable marketplace.

Literature on organizational design argued that structured management systems, complete with clear roles, responsibilities, and communication channels, are crucial for efficient public market operations. Researchers stress the importance of having dedicated market administrators, sanitation teams, monitoring staff, and revenue collectors supported by coherent workflows and reporting systems. This is directly relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because establishing a functional organizational structure ensures that daily operations run smoothly, issues are addressed promptly, and accountability mechanisms are properly enforced, all of which contribute to long-term market sustainability.

Studies on Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) showed that these arrangements can enhance infrastructure development, operational efficiency, and service quality when properly designed and monitored. Scholars highlight that PPP success depends on strong contracts, clear responsibilities, and sustained LGU oversight. However, PPPs can also lead to inequitable rental rates or vendor displacement if profit motives dominate. This literature is relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because it offers insights into prospect hybrid management models while warning against risks that could harm small vendors. The study can evaluate whether PPP elements may complement LGU-led operations in Gainza.

Research on local economic governance in developing countries highlighted persistent challenges such as resource shortages, informal economic practices, weak institutional capacity, and the need for decentralized economic planning. Scholars emphasize that strengthening local governance contributes to poverty reduction, employment creation, and improved service delivery. This literature is relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because Gainza, as a developing municipality, must improve governance systems to support its local economy, uplift small vendors, and manage public market spaces strategically to foster more inclusive and sustainable local growth.

Consumer protection studies underscored the importance of food safety, product quality standards, fair pricing, and hygienic market environments. Research shows that public markets with poor safety and sanitation pose health risks and undermine consumer trust, leading to reduced market utilization. Literature on food and market safety suggests that LGUs must enforce strict health codes, monitor vendor practices, and provide sanitation infrastructure. This is crucial for the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because improving consumer confidence through safety measures ensures stable market activity, enhances public welfare, and aligns Gainza with national consumer protection laws.

Studies on LGU-led market management emphasized the central role of local government systems in ensuring well-functioning public markets. Isolana (2021), in his study *Public–Private Partnership (PPP) as an Alternative Model to Public Infrastructure Development and Service Delivery*, analyzed LGU-managed markets after PPP transitions and found that weak institutional capacity, lack of maintenance, and inconsistent enforcement often lead to market deterioration. These findings were relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because they highlight the need for strengthening LGU systems, clearly defining management functions, and ensuring long-term operational planning to prevent deterioration and ensure sustainability.

Research on vendor permitting and regulation revealed numerous challenges facing LGUs and vendors. Solidum (2023), in her study on the *Status and Problems of Street Vendors*, found that unclear licensing policies, irregular enforcement, and bureaucratic procedures hinder compliance and create operational tension between vendors and local authorities. Similarly, Peimani et al. (2022) reviewed international cases of informal vending and concluded that overly strict or confusing regulatory systems push vendors into informality. These studies were relevant to the proposed Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because they emphasize the importance of developing a transparent, inclusive, and streamlined permitting system that encourages compliance, reduces conflict, and promotes legal market participation.

Studies on market operations highlighted operational challenges and revenue management issues in public markets. Abitria (2024), in her study of night market vendors in Albay, identified operational constraints such as inadequate facilities, inconsistent rental collection, and limited financial literacy among vendors. These findings were relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because they underline the need for improved stall systems, better financial tracking, adequate facilities, and clear operational guidelines to enhance both vendor performance and LGU revenue stability.

Comparative studies showed significant structural differences between public and privately managed markets. Isolana (2021) noted that while PPP-operated markets often exhibit efficient services and better infrastructure, they risk marginalizing low-income vendors due to higher stall fees and commercialization pressures. Chen (2012), studying informal market systems, argued that public markets provide essential social and economic functions that private markets may deprioritize. These findings are relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because they demonstrated the need to retain LGU control to ensure affordability and inclusiveness while adopting some efficiency-driven practices seen in private models to enhance sustainability.

Studies evaluating LGU transparency revealed that efficient public service delivery depends on strong accountability mechanisms. Tan and Flor (2022), in their study on LGU administrative efficiency, observed that transparent processes and digital reporting systems help reduce corruption and improve service speed. The study was relevant to the Sustainability Hub for the Gainza Public Market because transparent systems—especially in stall allocation, fee collection, and regulatory enforcement—will foster trust among vendors and consumers, strengthening the legitimacy and long-term sustainability of the market.

Studies on market accessibility emphasized that public markets play a vital role in ensuring equitable access to food, services, and livelihood opportunities. Armas et al. (2024), in developing a strategic plan for ambulant vendors, highlighted the importance of safe, accessible, and health-compliant market environments to support both vendors and consumers. These studies are relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because improving market

accessibility, walkability, safety, and sanitation will enhance community welfare and strengthen Gainza's local service delivery function.

Stakeholder perception studies revealed how governance decisions affect vendor behavior, compliance, and trust in local authorities. Kirumirah et al. (2024) demonstrated that when vendors perceive themselves as legitimate and included in market policies, they are more likely to follow regulations and participate in formal systems. Romero et al. (2024), in their action research with Manila street vendors, found that negative perceptions toward enforcement reduce cooperation and fuel policy resistance. These findings are relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because they emphasize the importance of participatory governance, consultations, and community involvement to ensure vendor acceptance of new systems.

Studies on inter-agency collaboration highlighted that effective market management requires coordinated actions between national and local agencies. When coordination is weak, policy duplication, inconsistent inspections, and operational conflicts occur. These findings are relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because establishing a coordinated system among agencies will support consistent standards for pricing, food safety, and supply chain regulation, and vendor compliance critical components of a sustainable and well-regulated market.

Case studies of public market failures revealed recurring issues such as deteriorating infrastructure, poor sanitation, mismanagement, and low vendor morale. Isolana (2021) documented how some revitalized PPP markets fell back into disorder when LGUs lacked systems to maintain cleanliness, governance, and infrastructure quality. Similar patterns were observed in various Philippine markets undergoing redevelopment without long-term sustainability plans. These studies were relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because they highlight potential pitfalls and underscore the importance of sustained LGU oversight, preventive maintenance, community involvement, and clear governance frameworks to avoid repeating past failures.

Studies on ICT in LGU management showed that digital tools improve efficiency, transparency, and service delivery. Tan and Taeihagh (2020), in their review of digital governance innovations in developing countries, found that ICT solutions—such as digital permitting, online monitoring, and data-driven regulation—enhance administrative control but require strong institutional readiness. Likewise, Cabreza (2021) demonstrated that e-governance systems reduced transaction times and promote transparency in LGU services. These findings were relevant to the Sustainable Hub for the Gainza Public Market because adopting digital tools for stall management, vendor registration, fee monitoring, and compliance tracking will modernize the market system and support long-term sustainability.

Gap Analysis

Across the theoretical and policy literatures there was strong consensus that public markets should be treated as multifunctional socio-economic infrastructures rather than mere retail spaces: Sotarauta & Beer (2020) on inclusive local economic development,— inclusivity, multi-stakeholder governance, and environmental responsibility. UN-Habitat and FAO guidance likewise emphasized accessibility, food-system resilience, and infrastructure that supports vendor livelihoods. All these literatures called for integrated policy responses (governance + design + community engagement) to achieve sustainability.

The literatures diverged in emphasis and scale. Sotarauta & Beer (2020) foreground governance and leadership at the meso/national-local interface, stressing institutional arrangements and place leadership; and green/eco-architecture literature focused more tightly on technical and material interventions (circular flows, waste systems, energy efficiency). Center on process and democratic legitimacy (co-production), which can sometimes conflict with technocratic efficiency arguments. UN-Habitat/FAO policy work is pragmatic and programmatic (standards, checklists), while academic theory often probes underlying causal mechanisms — so the literatures are complementary but sometimes operate on different problem definitions and recommended levers (institutional reform vs. design/technology vs. participatory process).

Research studies of Isolana 2021; Navarro & Llanto 2014; Solidum 2023; Peimani et al. 2022; Abitria 2024; Bromley 2000; Chen 2012; Tan & Flor 2022; Capuno 2019; Armas et al. 2024; Donovan 2008; Kirumirah et al. 2024; Romero et al. 2024; Brillantes & Fernandez 2013; Tan & Taeihagh 2020; Cabreza 2021, shared recurring findings: LGU capacity constraints, regulatory ambiguity, vendor precarity, sanitation/waste management gaps, and mixed results from PPPs or privatization. Many studies documented that without sustained institutional support, physical upgrades or PPP investments deteriorate (Isolana 2021). Several also showed that vendor perceptions and informal practices (Solidum; Kirumirah; Romero) strongly shape compliance and policy success.

Differences. Methodologically and substantively, the studies vary. Older syntheses were normative and conceptual; Peimani et al. (2022) provided systematic, cross-context comparisons of informal markets; Isolana (2021), Philippine-specific PPP evaluations; Abitria (2024), Solidum (2023), Kirumirah (2024), and Romero (2024) were micro-level empirical studies emphasizing vendor operations and perceptions. Studies on digitalization (Tan & Taeihagh 2020; Cabreza 2021) introduced ICT as a governance lever, while Armas et al. (2024) and FAO/UN-Habitat publications emphasize public health and food systems. Thus, studies differed in scale (macro policy vs. micro vendor), method (qualitative action research vs. quantitative audits), and emphasis (institutional design, technical upgrades, or community voice).

The evidence largely supported the high-level prescriptions of the theoretical literature: where governance is weak or exclusionary, markets underperform; where community participation and appropriate infrastructure exist, markets were more resilient — exactly as Sotarauta & Beer (2020). Research PPP evaluations (Isolana; Navarro & Llanto) validate theoretical cautions about institutional capacity and the risk of short-term gains without long-term governance. However, empirical work uncovers practical frictions that many theories under-specify. For example, co-production (Verschuere et al.) was theoretically attractive, but Solidum (2023) and Romero et al. (2024) showed how power imbalances, unclear legal status, and vendor survival pressures limit genuine co-production. Circular economy ideals (Geissdoerfer et al.) faced implementation barriers: space constraints in congested markets, limited municipal budgets, and informal waste streams make closed-loop systems harder to adopt than models suggest. Similarly, ICT proposals (Tan & Taeihagh; Cabreza) promised efficiency but empirical studies show digital exclusion risks for low-literacy vendors. In short, theory provides the “what” and “why,” while empirical studies specify the “how” and the constraints that must be resolved in real contexts.

The state-of-the-art showed strong agreement that sustainable market redevelopment requires multi-dimensional interventions (governance, design, community, waste systems, and monitoring). Differences across worked lie mainly in priority, sequencing, and contextual sensitivity. The Gainza study’s value proposition was its applied, integrated, equity-focused approach: it operationalizes theoretical frameworks (Sotarauta & Beer 2020 and responded

directly to empirical warnings from Isolana (2021), Solidum (2023), Abitria (2024), Tan & Flor (2022), and others by proposing sequenced, measurable, locally appropriate solutions that protect vendor livelihoods while modernizing infrastructure and governance. In doing so, the Gainza study addressed gaps in the literature and offers transferable lessons for other Philippine municipalities and similar developing-country contexts.

The literatures provided coherent frameworks (LED, co-production, circular economy), but empirical work shows implementation barriers; the Gainza study can bridge that gap by trialing integrated, locally feasible interventions. Multiple studies warn that physical upgrades or PPPs without institutional reform fail; Gainza's contribution is a tested sequencing roadmap. Many studies recommend TBL goals but offer few concrete indicators sets; Gainza can develop and validate a market-scale TBL monitoring toolkit. Prior evidence showed PPPs can increase efficiency but threaten inclusion; Gainza provided an empirical site to prototype contract and governance clauses that balance both.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a mixed-method research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the current status, sustainability level, and developmental prospects of the Gainza Public Market. Mixed methods were selected because they allowed the integration of numerical measurements with stakeholder perspectives, resulting in richer and more reliable findings. Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) emphasized that mixed-method designs are appropriate when quantitative and qualitative data together offer better insights into complex social and organizational issues than either approach alone.

The quantitative component employed descriptive research to measure sustainability indicators across economic, social, and environmental dimensions. This design aligned with the study's objective of identifying patterns, conditions, and gaps in market operations. Meanwhile, the qualitative component utilized phenomenological inquiry through interviews and focus group discussions to capture stakeholder experiences, perceptions, and expectations. According to Patton (2015), qualitative inquiry enables researchers to understand meanings individuals assign to their lived realities valuable in community-based and policy-related studies such as this.

Methods and Procedures

This study utilized three primary instruments were used for data collection:

1. **Survey Questionnaire.** A structured survey measured sustainability indicators such as physical infrastructure, management efficiency, economic viability, environmental practices, and institutional support. Items were adapted from sustainability assessment tools used in local economic development studies. The instrument underwent expert validation to ensure content accuracy. In the questionnaire, a 5-point Likert-type scale was used.
2. **Key Informant Interview (KII) Guide.** Semi-structured interviews explored the insights of LGU officials, market administrators, and partner agencies. The semi-structured format allowed flexibility while ensuring consistency across interviews. According to

Kallio et al. (2016), semi-structured interviews are ideal for exploring complex administrative processes and governance issues.

3. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. FGDs gathered perceptions from vendors and community members. Group discussions enabled interaction, supporting the collection of collective views and shared experiences relevant to community participation theory.

All instruments were pilot tested to determine clarity and reliability prior to formal data collection.

Also, the following procedures were undertaken:

1. Securing Permissions. Formal communication was sent to the Municipal Government of Gainza to request approval for data collection.
2. Conducting Surveys. Researchers administered printed or digital surveys to vendors and consumers. Respondents were briefed on the purpose and confidentiality of the study.
3. Key Informant Interviews. Scheduled interviews were conducted with municipal officials, market administrators, and agency representatives. Interviews were audio-recorded with consent.
4. Focus Group Discussions. FGDs consisting of 6–10 participants were held in Gainza Public Market, barangay hall, and in the municipal office. Discussions followed ethical guidelines to ensure voluntary participation.
5. Document Review. Secondary data (market records, ordinances, reports) were examined to support quantitative and qualitative findings.

This multi-method approach ensured triangulation, increasing the credibility of results (Denzin, 2012).

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the Consumers [A], Vendors [B], and LGU Officials [C] of the Municipality of Gainza for Calendar Year 2025 – 2026.

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents of the study.

Table 1. Respondents’ Profile

Distribution of Respondents of the Study

	N	%
A	70	66.67

B	30	28.57
C	5	4.76
	105	100

All the one hundred five (105) from various stakeholders for the said period were included as respondents in the study. It was a total enumeration as all of them actively participated in the study and no one was left-out to be excluded.

Ethical Considerations

Conducting this study involved paramount ethical considerations, starting with obtaining informed consent. It was crucial that all respondents fully understand the study's objectives, data usage, and their right to withdraw at any time without facing any consequences.

The second ethical consideration was the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents. Any information that could potentially revealed their identity should be anonymized to safeguard their privacy. Moreover, this research respected the autonomy and dignity of the respondents, acknowledging their decisions and safeguarding those with reduced autonomy. Respect for persons is an essential principle here.

In conducting research, the principle of beneficence called for aiming to do well and prevent harm. It entailed taking into account the possible advantages and disadvantages of the research for the respondents. Furthermore, the principle of justice was upheld, ensuring that the benefits and burdens of the research are distributed fairly among the participants.

Data Analysis Technique

The following statistical treatments were employed to derive meaningful findings that would substantiate the effectiveness of the proposed output:

1. Quantitative data were encoded and analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and weighted scoring. These measures allowed the evaluation of sustainability indicators and readiness for market redevelopment.
2. Qualitative data from KIIs and FGDs underwent thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) framework of coding, categorizing, and identifying emerging themes which provided meaningful interpretations of stakeholder perspectives and institutional issues.
3. Triangulation of survey results, qualitative insights, and documentary evidence strengthened the validity of the conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. STATUS FOR POSSIBLE FULL OPERATION OF THE GAINZA PUBLIC MARKET

The status of the Gainza Public Market provided an essential foundation for assessing its readiness for sustainable revitalization, particularly in terms of physical infrastructure,

management systems, and economic and business activity. Evaluating the existing physical facilities helped determine whether the market environment is adequately designed, functional, and safe to support both vendors and consumers. At the same time, a review of management practices revealed the effectiveness of the market's administrative structure, operational procedures, and regulatory enforcement, which directly influence efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction. Finally, examining the prevailing economic and business conditions clarifies the market's viability, competitiveness, and potential to stimulate local economic growth. Together, these dimensions offered a comprehensive understanding of the market's current performance and the areas requiring strategic improvement to ensure its sustainable future operation.

a. Physical Infrastructure

In Table 2.1, the findings revealed that the physical structure of the Gainza Public Market is generally rated Poor, as indicated by an average weighted mean of 2.95. Among the indicators assessed, only the adequacy of the market building and stalls obtained a Fair rating (AWM = 3.4), making it the highest-rated aspect. In contrast, water and sanitation facilities, accessibility features, and safety and security systems all shared the lowest rating of Poor (AWM = 2.8), suggesting consistent deficiencies in these areas. Overall, the results highlight those structural inadequacies are most pronounced in essential facilities and systems required for functional, safe, and sustainable market operations.

These findings suggested that while the market structure may still be functional in terms of basic stall adequacy, critical support facilities may be underdeveloped or poorly maintained. The low scores in sanitation, accessibility, and security could be attributed to limited LGU resources, aging infrastructure, or insufficient prioritization in local development planning. It is possible that the market's reliance on outdated utilities contributed to the poor quality of water and waste systems, while the inadequate accessibility rating may be because of narrow roads, lack of parking spaces, or poorly managed traffic flow. The low-rating for safety systems may indicate either a lack of equipment, absence of personnel, or operational challenges that hinder security enforcement. These conditions collectively point to systemic issues affecting the market's ability to meet minimum standards for public facilities.

Table 2.1

Status of Operation of the Gainza Public Market in terms of Physical Structure

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Adequacy of market building and stalls.	3.4	Fair	1

Availability and quality of water, sanitation, and waste facilities.	2.8	Poor	2
Accessibility (roads, transport, parking, loading/unloading).	2.8	Poor	2
Safety and security systems (lighting, CCTV, guard presence).	2.8	Poor	2
Average Weighted Mean	2.95		
Interpretation		Poor	

The consistent poor ratings across key functional facilities indicated that the physical environment of the Gainza Public Market does not sufficiently support safe, hygienic, and accessible commerce. This suggested that the market's current infrastructure fails to meet both user expectations and institutional requirements for sustainable and inclusive public market operations. The pattern of low scores in sanitation and safety showed that existing facilities may not comply with health and security standards, which could deter consumers and negatively affect economic activity. Meanwhile, the poor accessibility rating indicated that mobility constraints may be limiting vendor and consumer flow, reducing the market's overall efficiency. Collectively, the results indicated that substantial upgrades are necessary to improve the market's operational resilience and to align its facilities with modern sustainability and governance benchmarks.

These findings aligned with Sustainable Development Governance Theory, which emphasizes that effective public infrastructure must integrate environmental, economic, and social dimensions to support long-term community welfare. The poor ratings for sanitation, safety, and accessibility reflected the governance challenges Meadowcroft identifies—specifically, the gaps between policy goals and actual implementation. Similar studies on developing-country markets also highlighted infrastructure deficits as barriers to sustainable operations, reinforcing that the Gainza Public Market's situation was not isolated but reflective of broader structural issues in local governance. However, the relatively fair rating for market stall adequacy slightly diverged from literature where physical overcrowding is typically the most critical issue, suggesting that Gainza's main concerns lie more in utilities and support systems. Overall, the results showed how infrastructure weaknesses impede sustainable governance, underscoring the need for a more integrated and forward-looking approach to public market development.

Given the identified weaknesses, the LGU should prioritize upgrading water, sanitation, waste management, and safety systems, as these directly affect public health and market reliability. Infrastructure improvements such as installing proper drainage, expanding parking and loading zones, and enhancing security equipment must be pursued through phased, budget-feasible plans. Establishing partnerships with provincial agencies or NGOs may also help address resource limitations. This study's reliance on LGU evaluation data may limit generalizability, as ratings reflected institutional perspectives rather than user experiences; future research should include consumer surveys, technical assessments, and engineering audits. It is recommended that subsequent studies explore cost-benefit analyses and sustainability models to guide the development of a proposed Sustainable Market Hub that is both functional and future-ready.

b. Management

The results in Table 2.2 showed that the management of the Gainza Public Market is rated very poorly across all indicators, with the highest mean score of only 1.6 for the

effectiveness of the current administration system. The lowest ratings—1.0—were recorded for transparency, enforcement of rules, and responsiveness to stakeholders, indicating consistently weak governance practices. Overall, the average weighted mean of 1.15 clearly reflected a severely deficient management system, suggesting that significant issues exist in accountability, regulatory enforcement, and stakeholder engagement.

These results may indicate that the current management structure is struggling due to limited administrative capacity, inadequate systems, or possible institutional fragmentation. The very poor ratings for transparency and enforcement could be because operational processes are unclear, record-keeping is inconsistent, or market policies are not actively implemented. It is also possible that the low responsiveness to vendor and customer concerns reflects a lack of formal feedback mechanisms or insufficient staffing. These patterns suggested that the governance approach may be reactive rather than proactive, which may inhibit the market's ability to operate effectively and sustainably.

Table 2.2

Status of Operation of the Gainza Public Market in terms of Management

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Effectiveness of current market administration/management system.	1.6	Very Poor	1
Transparency and accountability of market operations.	1	Very Poor	2
Enforcement of rules, regulations, and fee collection.	1	Very Poor	2
Responsiveness to vendors' and customers' concerns.	1	Very Poor	2
Average Weighted Mean	1.15		
Interpretation		Very Poor	

The findings indicated that the management of the Gainza Public Market is critically weak and poses a major barrier to its potential reopening or revitalization. The consistently low scores suggested that inadequate governance systems undermine accountability, public trust, and operational efficiency—all essential components of sustainable market management. This pattern showed that the LGU's capacity to administer the market is insufficient to meet the needs of vendors, customers, and regulatory demands. Such results also point to structural gaps that prevent effective rule implementation, stakeholder communication, and proper market oversight, indicating that comprehensive administrative reform is necessary for sustainable market development.

These findings aligned with Meadowcroft's (2017) Sustainable Development Governance Theory, which emphasizes the role of capable and transparent institutions in steering public systems toward long-term sustainability. Similar to Navarro and Llanto's (2014) observation on governance gaps in public-private partnerships in the Philippines, the results showed significant deficiencies in administrative capacity and accountability. Furthermore, Braun and Clarke's (2006) discussions on thematic analysis suggested that recurring governance issues—such as weak enforcement and low responsiveness—form clear patterns that require systemic intervention. Compared with existing research, the current results confirmed that weak local governance often hinders public market functionality, underscoring the importance of

institutional strengthening. These findings contributed to the understanding that sustainable local economic hubs require not only physical infrastructure but also strong managerial systems.

Based on the findings, it was recommended that the LGU implement a comprehensive market management reform strategy, including capacity-building for staff, establishment of transparent administrative procedures, and creation of clear enforcement protocols. Introducing digital tools for monitoring, fee collection, and grievance reporting could enhance transparency and accountability. A participatory governance model involving vendors and consumers should also be adopted to improve responsiveness and ensure shared responsibility. The study acknowledged limitations such as reliance on self-reported data and possible respondent bias, which may affect generalizability. Future research should include observational audits, financial assessments, and comparative studies with well-managed local markets to provide deeper insights and guide long-term policy development.

c. Economics and Business activities

As shown in Table 2.3, the results stated that the Gainza Public Market is performing poorly in all aspects of its economic and business operations, with all indicators receiving low ratings. The highest-rated item—competitiveness compared to nearby municipalities—received only a 2.8, still falling within the Poor interpretation, indicating that the market underperforms relative to neighboring towns. Meanwhile, the affordability of stall rental and market fees and the level of business activity and vendor participation emerged as the lowest-ranked indicators, both scoring 2.2 and interpreted as Poor. With an overall Average Weighted Mean of 2.45, which is classified as Very Poor, the table highlights a consistently weak economic environment within the market.

These findings suggested that the economic struggles of the Gainza Public Market may be linked to insufficient business participation and a limited variety of goods and services, which could discourage customer patronage. It is possible that high perceived risks or low profitability discourage vendors from engaging in full-scale business operations, resulting in reduced vendor presence and lower economic activity. The poor affordability rating also reflected fee structures that, while not explicitly high, may still feel unreasonable relative to the low level of customer traffic or revenue potential. Furthermore, the market's weak competitiveness may be because nearby municipalities offer better infrastructure, stronger customer bases, or more established commercial systems. Overall, the results indicate that structural and demand-related challenges may be undermining the market's economic viability.

Table 2.3

Status of Operation of the Gainza Public Market in terms of economics and business activities

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Affordability of stall rental and market fees.	2.2	Poor	3
Competitiveness of the market compared to nearby municipalities.	2.8	Poor	1

Availability of diverse goods and services.	2.6	Poor	2
Level of business activity and vendor participation.	2.2	Poor	3
Average Weighted Mean	2.45		
Interpretation		Very Poor	

The consistently poor scores across all indicators indicated that the Gainza Public Market is not functioning as an economically viable local commercial hub. The low level of vendor participation showed that the market currently lacks the economic dynamism needed to attract both traders and consumers, while the limited diversity of goods suggests that customers may not perceive the market as a primary shopping destination. Likewise, the insufficient competitiveness indicated that surrounding markets may be capturing the economic opportunities that Gainza is unable to harness. These results collectively point to systemic challenges that hinder the market's ability to stimulate local enterprise development or contribute meaningfully to the municipality's economic growth. The overall evaluation of Very Poor underscored that significant improvements are necessary to transform the market into a sustainable economic driver.

The findings resonated with the principles of the Inclusive Local Economic Development Theory (Sotarauta & Beer, 2020), which emphasizes that local markets thrive only when governance structures, vendor support systems, and economic conditions work together to create inclusive growth. Similar to Solidum's (2023) findings on the challenges faced by street vendors in the Philippines, particularly low income, unstable demand, and poor market environments, the Gainza Public Market demonstrates the same vulnerabilities, affirming broader national trends. However, the persistently low economic performance in Gainza suggested deeper structural constraints than those noted in comparative studies, possibly exacerbated by weaker local economic governance. This comparison strengthened the interpretation that the market's current operations fall short of principles promoting equitable and competitive local economic participation. Ultimately, the findings highlighted the urgent importance of revitalizing the market's economic foundations to align with development frameworks and ensure long-term community benefit.

Given the findings, the LGU should prioritize strengthening vendor participation by redesigning fee structures, offering incentives, and improving market facilities to enhance the affordability and attractiveness of doing business in Gainza. Introducing programs such as vendor capacity-building, product diversification initiatives, and targeted marketing campaigns can also help improve market competitiveness. However, limitations such as the small sample size, reliance on LGU perspectives, and possible response biases may have influenced the results, suggesting that future studies should include broader stakeholder groups—such as consumers, suppliers, and external business experts—to provide a more holistic understanding. Further research could also examine the economic impacts of neighboring markets to identify competitive strategies. By addressing these areas, Gainza can work toward establishing a more vibrant, sustainable, and economically inclusive public market ecosystem.

II. PROSPECTS OF FULL OPERATION OF THE GAINZA PUBLIC MARKET

Understanding the prospects of the Gainza Public Market involves examining the forward-looking factors that influenced its viability as a catalyst for local development. The economic growth potential highlighted opportunities for increasing market activity, attracting vendors and consumers, and supporting livelihood expansion within the municipality. Equally significant were sustainability and environmental considerations, which explore how the market

can adopt eco-friendly practices, resilient infrastructure, and responsible resource management to ensure long-term functionality. Moreover, policy and institutional readiness assessed the capability of the LGU to implement regulations, mobilize resources, and provide strategic governance needed for market activation. Together, these prospects outline the pathways through which the Gainza Public Market can evolve into a sustainable, inclusive, and economically vibrant community hub.

a. Economic Growth

The results in Table 3.1 showed that the Gainza Public Market demonstrates a generally positive outlook for full operation in terms of economic growth potential, with an overall moderate interpretation (AWM = 3.93). The highest-rated indicators were the market's potential to increase local government revenues and its capacity to support local farmers and producers, both receiving a high rating (AWM = 4.00). Meanwhile, the lowest score—though still within the moderate range—pertained to the market's ability to attract more vendors and businesses (AWM = 3.8). Overall, the findings highlighted those economic prospects for market revitalization are promising, though the level of vendor attraction remains slightly behind revenue and producer-support potential.

Table 3.1

Prospects of Full Operation of Gainza Public Market in terms of Economic Growth Potential

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Potential to attract more vendors and businesses.	3.8	Moderate	2
Potential to increase local government revenues.	4	High	1
Potential to support local farmers and producers.	4	High	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.93		
Interpretation		Moderate	

The overall results indicated that the Gainza Public Market holds strong potential to function as an economic driver once fully operational, particularly in strengthening local supply chains and increasing municipal income. The high ratings on revenue generation and farmer support suggested that the LGU views the market as a strategic mechanism for revitalizing local productivity and expanding fiscal capacity. The moderately high potential for vendor attraction shows that while interest exists, further structural and promotional interventions are needed to ensure consistent vendor participation. These results collectively reflected an economic environment that is receptive to market revitalization, provided that enabling conditions—such as improved infrastructure, effective management, and vendor incentives—are adequately addressed.

These findings aligned with Sustainable Development Governance Theory (Meadowcroft, 2017), which emphasizes the role of institutions in steering local economic systems toward long-term viability. The observed potential for revenue growth and producer supports echoed Meadowcroft's argument that local governance structures play a critical role in shaping sustainable market ecosystems. Moreover, the results supported insights from Armas et al. (2024), whose work on ambulant vendors in the Philippines highlights how strategic frameworks and supportive environments significantly improve market participation and

economic outcomes. Similar to their findings, this study showed that clear institutional commitment and structured economic planning enhance market prospects. While the slightly lower score on vendor attraction indicated gaps, it also expanded current understanding by showing that even with strong institutional backing, vendor confidence may lag without targeted interventions. Overall, the results reinforced the importance of governance-led strategies in improving local markets and illustrate how the Gainza Public Market can contribute meaningfully to local development trajectories.

Based on these findings, the LGU should prioritize incentive packages for vendors, such as reduced initial rental rates, startup assistance, or promotional campaigns to strengthen vendor attraction, which scored slightly lower than other indicators. Strengthening partnerships with local farmers through procurement programs and dedicated selling zones can further enhance the market's high potential to support producers. However, the study's reliance on LGU perceptions presents a limitation, as administrative perspectives may not fully reflect ground-level economic realities; thus, incorporating longitudinal vendor surveys and market foot-traffic assessments in future research would provide a more comprehensive view. Future studies should also investigate competitive pressures from nearby markets and explore demand-side factors influencing consumer behavior. These actions will help refine strategies for full market operation and ensure that the Gainza Public Market evolves into a sustainable economic hub.

b. Sustainability and Environment

In Table 3.2, the results showed that the LGU perceives strong environmental potential for the full operation of the Gainza Public Market, with the highest rating given to its ability to adopt eco-friendly waste management practices. This was closely followed by the potential for energy-efficient and green infrastructure, while the promotion of sustainable consumption and production received the lowest—but still favorable—rating. Overall, the average weighted mean indicated a high level of sustainability prospects, suggesting that the LGU views the market as highly viable in terms of environmental performance and future green development pathways.

Table 3.2

Prospects of Full Operation of Gainza Public Market in terms of Sustainability and Environmental

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Potential to adopt eco-friendly waste management practices.	4.2	High	1
Potential for energy-efficient and green infrastructure.	4	High	2
Potential to promote sustainable consumption and	3.8	Moderate	3

production.			
Average Weighted Mean	4.0		
Interpretation		High	

These findings may indicate that the LGU has already identified or envisioned concrete opportunities to integrate sustainability practices within the market's future operations. It is possible that existing LGU waste management programs or partnerships make eco-friendly practices more feasible, resulting in higher confidence in this area. Meanwhile, the slightly lower rating on sustainable consumption and production could be because current community behaviors or vendor practices may not yet fully align with sustainability principles. The patterns in the ratings may also reflect varying levels of readiness or available resources within the LGU for implementing different types of environmental initiatives.

The results indicated that the LGU strongly recognizes the environmental potential of the Gainza Public Market and views sustainability as a central component of its future operation. The high ratings for eco-friendly waste management and green infrastructure suggested that the LGU is prepared—or at least highly willing—to invest in systems that support long-term ecological resilience. Furthermore, the moderate rating on sustainable consumption and production illustrated that while foundational structures for sustainability exist, behavioral and market-based changes may still be needed to fully realize these goals. Overall, the findings showed that the LGU envisions the market as a strategic platform for advancing local environmental governance.

These findings aligned closely with the Urban Sustainability and Circular Economy Theory of Geissdoerfer et al. (2017), which emphasized the importance of integrating waste reduction, resource efficiency, and sustainable design into local development processes. The LGU's strong environmental outlook was also consistent with Sotarauta and Beer's (2020) work on inclusive local economic development, which argued that forward-thinking leadership and institutional capacity enhance sustainability outcomes. Compared to existing literature on public market revitalization, the results reinforced the idea that local governments play a critical role in steering green transitions at the community level. This connection suggested that the Gainza Public Market has the potential to serve as a local model for integrating sustainability into public economic spaces, contributing meaningfully to broader environmental governance efforts.

Based on the findings, the LGU should prioritize the development of a comprehensive sustainability framework that includes waste segregation systems, renewable energy options, and green building design standards for the market. It is recommended that feasibility studies be conducted to determine cost-efficient energy solutions and that capacity-building programs be provided for vendors to promote sustainable consumption and production practices. Limitations of this study may include potential response biases and the absence of detailed technical assessments of environmental infrastructure, which could affect the depth of interpretation. Future research should explore the economic viability of specific green technologies for the market and investigate community readiness for adopting sustainable practices.

c. Policy and Institutional

The findings in Table 3.3 indicated that the Gainza Local Government Unit (LGU) expresses strong confidence in its policy and institutional readiness to support the full operation of the public market as a sustainable hub. The highest-rated indicator was the institutional capacity of the LGU to manage a sustainable hub (AWM = 4.6), suggesting that governance

structures and operational systems are perceived as well established. This was followed by strong support from local ordinances and policies (AWM = 4.4) and the alignment of market operations with LGU development plans (AWM = 4.2), which also reflect high levels of readiness. Overall, the data showed a consistently high level of institutional preparedness (overall AWM = 4.4), underscoring a favorable environment for the market's transition to full sustainable operation.

Table 3.3

Prospects of Full Operation of Gainza Public Market in terms of Policy and Institutional according to the LGU Officials

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Alignment of market operations with LGU development plans.	4.2	High	3
Support from local ordinances and policies.	4.4	High	2
Institutional capacity of the LGU to manage a sustainable hub.	4.6	High	1
Average Weighted Mean	4.4		
Interpretation		High	

These results may indicate that the LGU has already made considerable groundwork toward establishing governance mechanisms that support sustainable market operations. The high ratings could be because the LGU has integrated the public market into its broader development agenda, possibly aligning it with economic, environmental, or community-based goals. It is also possible that existing ordinances or policy reforms have recently strengthened institutional systems, resulting in increased confidence among LGU respondents. Additionally, the strong perceived institutional capacity may be a reflection of ongoing initiatives or prior experiences managing community-based or economic infrastructures, which could contribute to the LGU's optimism regarding the market's full operation.

The consistently high scores suggested that the LGU's policy framework and institutional strengths indicate a robust foundation for the sustainable operation of the Gainza Public Market. These findings showed that governance structures, policy support, and organizational capacity are functioning cohesively, providing a strong enabling environment for implementing sustainability initiatives. The high rating for institutional capacity, in particular, indicated that the LGU is not only prepared administratively but also organizationally to manage and sustain long-term operations. This pattern signalled that policy and governance elements are likely to play a central role in ensuring the market becomes a successful and enduring sustainable hub within the municipality.

The results aligned with Community Co-Production Theory (Verschuere et al., 2018), which emphasizes the critical role of institutional readiness and governance structures in enabling collaborative public service delivery. The strong institutional capacity reflected in the findings resonates with the theory's assertion that effective public service outcomes require competent and well-prepared government actors. Additionally, studies such as Navarro & Llanto (2014) on Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in the Philippines highlighted that institutional strength and policy coherence are key determinants of project success—similar to the readiness seen in the LGU's market operations. These findings reinforced the broader understanding that robust policy alignment and institutional capacity are central to achieving sustainable local development. Ultimately, this underscored the importance of strong governance foundations in ensuring that the Gainza Public Market operates effectively as a sustainable hub.

Based on the findings, the LGU should continue strengthening its institutional structures by developing clear implementation protocols, refining existing ordinances, and establishing dedicated sustainability units or committees to ensure smooth market operations. It is recommended that capacity-building programs be provided to sustain institutional effectiveness, particularly in areas such as environmental management, market regulation, and stakeholder engagement. While the results indicate high readiness, the study may be limited by reliance on LGU self-assessment, which could introduce positive bias; thus, future research should triangulate with external audits or performance evaluations. Additional studies may also explore cross-LGU comparisons or assess long-term governance outcomes to further validate institutional readiness. Ensuring ongoing stakeholder participation and periodic policy review will help maintain momentum and support the market's sustainable transition.

III. LEVEL OF SUSTAINABILITY OF GAINZA PUBLIC MARKET

The level of sustainability of the Gainza Public Market was assessed across three core dimensions - economic growth, environmental sustainability, and policy and institutional readiness - to determine its long-term viability as a community-oriented commercial hub. Evaluating these dimensions provided an integrated understanding of how the market performs in terms of economic resilience, operational efficiency, and ecological responsibility, while also examining whether existing governing structures and policies support sustainable market operations. This section established how well the market aligns with sustainable development principles by analyzing its economic performance, environmental management practices, and institutional capacity, thereby offering a comprehensive basis for identifying strengths, gaps, and opportunities for strategic improvement.

a. Economic Sustainability

In Table 4.1.1, the results showed that the vendors and stallholders perceive the LGU's sustainable procurement practices as moderately sustainable, as indicated by the overall AWM of 3.33. Among the indicators, awareness of opportunities to supply goods for LGU programs received the highest rating (3.5), suggesting relatively stronger engagement between market stakeholders and local government procurement initiatives. Meanwhile, inclusion of sustainability criteria in LGU procurement processes was rated the lowest (3.2), indicating that some stakeholders believe these environmental considerations may not yet be consistently applied. Overall, the findings highlight moderate progress toward SDG 12.7.1, with room for improvement across all procurement dimensions.

Table 4.1.1

Level of Sustainability of Gainza Public Market in terms of Sustainable Procurement and SDG 12.7.1 (Policies & Priorities) according to the Vendors and Stallholders

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Sustainability criteria are included in LGU procurement.	3.2	Moderately Sustainable	4
Priority is given to MSMEs, farmers, and women in contract awards.	3.3	Moderately Sustainable	2
I am aware of opportunities to supply goods for LGU programs.	3.5	Moderately Sustainable	1

Life-cycle costing and green sourcing are embedded in procurement.	3.3	Moderately Sustainable	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.33		
Interpretation		Moderately Sustainable	

The moderately sustainable rating suggested that while sustainable procurement practices are present, they may not yet be fully institutionalized or consistently communicated to vendors. The relatively higher score for stakeholder awareness of supply opportunities may indicate that information campaigns or LGU outreach programs are somewhat effective, although their scope could still be limited. The lower rating for sustainability criteria in procurement could be because vendors may not clearly see how such criteria influence actual contract awarding, or it may be that LGU procurement officers have not fully integrated environmental standards into evaluation tools. These patterns may be related to gaps in policy implementation, limited training, or insufficient vendor capacity to meet sustainability requirements.

The results indicated that the LGU's current procurement system supports the inclusion of sustainability principles but has not yet reached full maturity, as reflected by the consistently moderate scores. The findings showed that stakeholders recognize efforts to prioritize MSMEs, farmers, and women in procurement, which aligns with inclusive economic growth objectives. However, the moderate rating for life-cycle costing and green sourcing indicates that more advanced sustainability tools are not yet widely practiced or fully understood among vendors. This suggested that while sustainable procurement is underway, the system still requires stronger institutional mechanisms, clearer guidelines, and broader capacity-building to achieve higher levels of sustainability performance aligned with SDG 12.7.1.

These findings aligned with Sustainable Development Governance Theory (Meadowcroft, 2017), which emphasized that sustainability transitions require strong institutional coordination and gradual policy integration—both of which appear to be developing but not yet fully realized in the LGU's procurement system. The moderate results also echoed Solidum (2023), who found that many Filipino vendors face information gaps and institutional barriers that limit their participation in formal procurement opportunities. Similar to prior studies on sustainable governance, the results confirmed that stakeholder participation increases when policies are clearly communicated, but genuine sustainable procurement requires deeper structural reforms. Overall, the findings reinforced the importance of strengthening local governance systems to enhance sustainability outcomes and ensure inclusive participation in public procurement.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that the LGU strengthen its sustainable procurement framework by developing clearer guidelines, integrating measurable sustainability criteria into procurement documents, and expanding capacity-building programs for vendors on green sourcing and life-cycle costing. The LGU should also institutionalize regular information drives and transparent communication channels to ensure that MSMEs, farmers, and women-led enterprises can access procurement opportunities. Study limitations may include potential vendor misunderstanding of procurement concepts or limited familiarity with SDG-related processes, which could affect how indicators were rated. Future research may explore qualitative interviews with procurement officials and vendors to capture deeper insights into barriers, and comparative studies with other municipalities may help identify best practices for improving sustainable procurement systems.

Table 4.1.2 results showed that consumers and market users demonstrate mixed but generally neutral sustainability perspectives, with a slight inclination toward supporting eco-friendly practices. The highest-rated indicator was consumer support for vendors who use eco-friendly packaging and sustainable practices, which received an “Agree” interpretation, suggested that this aspect resonates more strongly with the public. Meanwhile, willingness to pay more for sustainably produced goods scored the lowest but still remained within the neutral range, indicating hesitancy toward cost-related sustainability choices. Overall, the average weighted mean of 3.94 reflects a neutral stance, implying that while consumers recognize the value of sustainability practices, they may not yet be fully committed to making consistent, sustainable purchasing decisions.

Table 4.1.2

Level of Sustainability of Gainza Public Market according to Consumers and Market Users

Indicator	AWM	Interpretaion	Rank
I prefer to buy products that are locally sourced.	3.96	Neutral	2
I support vendors who use eco-friendly packaging and practices.	4.04	Agree	1
Inclusive facilities (for PWDs, elderly, women) influence my choice of market.	3.9	Neutral	3
I am willing to pay slightly more for sustainably produced goods.	3.86	Neutral	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.94		
Interpretation		Neutral	

These findings may suggest that consumers are becoming more aware of environmentally responsible market practices, yet their behavior is still influenced by practical considerations such as price and convenience. The higher rating for supporting eco-friendly packaging could be because such practices are easily visible and do not require additional financial commitment from consumers. On the other hand, the lower rating for willingness to pay more may be related to economic constraints or limited awareness of the long-term benefits of sustainable consumption. It is possible that consumers value sustainability but remain cautious about actions that directly affect their budget, especially in local market contexts where affordability is a primary concern.

The results indicated that sustainability awareness among market users is present but not yet strong enough to drive more transformative consumer behavior. The strong support for eco-friendly packaging showed that visible, tangible sustainability practices have a higher impact on consumer attitudes compared to practices requiring financial sacrifice. This suggested that sustainability efforts at the Gainza Public Market may gain more traction if they prioritize highly visible and accessible initiatives. The overall neutral interpretation showed that consumers are open to sustainability but require further motivation, education, or incentives to fully integrate sustainability into their purchasing decisions.

These findings align with the Inclusive Local Economic Development Theory (Sotarauta & Beer, 2020), which emphasizes that community participation in market systems emerged gradually and requires both awareness and structural support. Similar to Abitria's (2024) findings on night market vendors in Albay, consumer preferences tend to remain neutral when

sustainability practices do not directly affect convenience or pricing. The consistency between this study and prior research strengthens the argument that consumer-driven sustainability relied heavily on the interplay between awareness, affordability, and accessibility. This suggested that the Gainza Public Market's sustainability initiatives must be both socially inclusive and economically practical to influence behavior meaningfully. Ultimately, the results contributed to a broader understanding that sustainable market development requires not only provider-driven initiatives but also gradual shifts in consumer preferences shaped by education and policy.

b. Social Sustainability

The findings in Table 4.2 showed that vendors and stallholders perceive the social sustainability and accessibility of the Gainza Public Market as moderately sustainable overall, with an AWM of 3.28. The highest-rated indicator was the presence of vendor support programs for vulnerable groups, which received an AWM of 3.53, suggesting positive efforts toward inclusivity. Meanwhile, facilities accessibility for persons with disabilities (3.37) and the clarity of pathways and signage (3.33) were also rated moderately sustainable. However, gender-sensitive facilities emerged as the lowest indicator with an AWM of 2.90, placing it in the "unsustainable" category, indicating a clear gap in gender-responsive infrastructure.

Table 4.2

Level of Sustainability of Gainza Public Market in terms of Social Sustainability and Accessibility according to the Vendors and Stallholders

Indicator	AWM	Interpretaion	Rank
Facilities are accessible for persons with disabilities.	3.37	Moderately Sustainable	2
Pathways, signage, and layout are clear for all customer groups.	3.33	Moderately Sustainable	3
Gender-sensitive facilities (restrooms, changing rooms) are available.	2.9	Unsustainable	4
Vendor support programs exist for vulnerable groups (women, PWDs).	3.53	Moderately Sustainable	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.28		
Interpretation		Moderately Sustainable	

The results indicated that the market shows progress in promoting inclusivity, but critical gaps remain, particularly in addressing the needs of women and gender-diverse groups. The strong rating for vendor support programs suggested that the market is becoming a platform that empowers vulnerable groups, which strengthened its social sustainability performance. However, the unsustainable rating for gender-sensitive facilities suggests that structural and institutional barriers persist, undermining full inclusivity. This imbalance between program-based support and infrastructural limitations indicates that while social responsibility is acknowledged, it is not yet holistically implemented across all aspects of market operations.

These results aligned with the Sustainable Development Governance Theory (Meadowcroft, 2017), which emphasizes that sustainability requires coherent institutional actions rather than isolated initiatives. The disparity between support programs and physical facilities reflected what Meadowcroft describes as the gap between policy intention and operational capacity. Furthermore, the findings resonated with Cabreza (2021), who noted that LGUs often

excel in administrative service delivery improvements yet lag in infrastructure modernization due to bureaucratic and resource constraints. Similar to other Philippine local public markets, the Gainza Public Market demonstrates emerging governance responsiveness but still faces challenges in meeting universal accessibility standards. These findings reinforced the importance of integrating accessibility, gender equity, and social inclusiveness into the core design of public infrastructures.

c. Environment Sustainability

In Table 4.3, the findings revealed that the LGU considers the environmental sustainability of the Gainza Public Market as moderately sustainable, as reflected in the overall average weighted mean of 3.6. Among the indicators, the implementation of waste reduction and recycling practices received the highest rating, indicating stronger performance and prioritization in this area. Pollution minimization followed closely, while adaptability to climate change and disaster resilience ranked lowest, suggesting that this aspect requires further enhancement despite still being rated moderately sustainable overall. These results highlighted the LGU's generally positive but uneven performance across the different dimensions of environmental sustainability.

The results show that the LGU demonstrated a moderate level of commitment to environmental sustainability, with clear strengths in waste management but remaining vulnerabilities in climate resilience. The consistency of moderately sustainable ratings across indicators indicated that environmental initiatives are present but not optimized. The relatively lower score for climate adaptability suggests that the market's current infrastructure and systems may not yet fully support disaster preparedness and long-term climate resilience. Overall, the findings indicated that while progress is evident, substantial development is still needed to ensure that environmental sustainability becomes a fully integrated pillar of market operations.

Table 4.3

Level of Sustainability of Gainza Public Market in Terms of Environmental Sustainability

Indicator	AWM	Interpretation	Rank
Implementation of waste reduction and recycling practices.	3.8	Moderately Sustainable	1
Minimization of pollution (solid waste, wastewater, noise).	3.6	Moderately Sustainable	2
Adaptability to climate change and disaster resilience.	3.4	Moderately Sustainable	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.6		

Interpretation	Moderately Sustainable	
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These results aligned with the Community Co-Production Theory of Verschuere et al. (2018), which emphasizes shared responsibility between government and stakeholders in delivering sustainable services. The findings suggested that environmental sustainability in Gainza Public Market partly depends on coordinated action between the LGU and market users, reflecting the theory's emphasis on joint governance. Similarly, the moderate sustainability rating was consistent with Navarro and Llanto's (2014) assessment of PPPs in the Philippines, which found that environmental components are often present but underdeveloped due to resource constraints and implementation gaps. Thus, the present study reinforced existing literature by showing that while environmental policies exist at the LGU level, full operationalization—especially on climate resilience—remains a challenge. This contributed to a deeper understanding of how local markets progress toward sustainability within real-world constraints.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that the LGU intensify its initiatives on climate change adaptation by investing in disaster-resilient infrastructure, establishing clearer evacuation and emergency response systems, and integrating climate risk assessments into market planning. Strengthening pollution control measures—such as wastewater treatment and noise regulation—should also be prioritized to complement existing waste management efforts. The study's limitations, such as reliance on LGU self-assessment and the absence of external environmental audits, may have influenced the results; thus, future research should incorporate third-party evaluations and comparative assessments with other public markets. Further studies may also explore the role of community participation in enhancing environmental resilience, ensuring that the Gainza Public Market can evolve into a fully sustainable local economic hub.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES FOR GAINZA PUBLIC MARKET AS A SUSTAINABLE HUB

This study culminated in the strategic synthesis of empirical findings into a formalized framework designed for local governance and operational management. By integrating the data collected from the assessment of physical, social, and economic variables, this phase focused on the creation of a comprehensive set of Implementation Guidelines. These guidelines acted as a vital bridge between theoretical sustainability concepts and the practical, day-to-day administration of public infrastructure. Their purpose was to provide the Local Government Unit (LGU) with an evidence-based roadmap that addressed identified systemic gaps, ensuring that the transition into a resilient community hub was guided by structured protocols rather than fragmented interventions. Ultimately, this output served as the functional application of the study's results, transforming academic inquiry into a tangible resource for regional development and institutional accountability.

IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES FOR GAINZA PUBLIC MARKET AS A SUSTAINABLE HUB

I. RATIONALE

The Gainza Public Market is envisioned to serve as a central economic and social hub that strengthens local livelihoods, enhances service delivery, and stimulates inclusive economic growth within the municipality. However, baseline findings from the quantitative data, open-

ended responses, and FGDs reveal that the market currently faces significant operational, structural, and institutional challenges. These include limited foot traffic due to its distant location, incomplete facilities such as water supply and drainage, inadequate sanitation, and insufficient stall organization. Consumers cited distance and transportation as their most common barriers, while vendors highlighted market inactivity, low customer turnout, and lack of basic utilities as the biggest constraints to sustaining their business operations. These persistent issues hinder the market's ability to function as a viable trading center and prevent it from achieving its full development potential.

The assessment also revealed gaps in the market's accessibility and inclusion mechanisms, with consumers expressing only neutral satisfaction regarding pathways, signage, and the preparedness of staff to serve vulnerable groups. These findings underscore the need for improved infrastructure aligned with universal design principles, better orientation for market personnel, and clearer protocols to ensure that all users including PWDs, senior citizens, and low-income households can access the market safely and comfortably. Without such measures, the public market risks remaining underutilized, inequitable, and disconnected from the needs of its intended beneficiaries.

Furthermore, the results show that activation readiness and community involvement remain at a neutral level. While consumers are moderately willing to provide feedback and receive updates on market revival plans, participation in consultations or engagement activities remains uncertain. This indicates that community members are not fully integrated into planning and decision-making processes, likely due to limited communication, inadequate awareness mechanisms, or weak participatory structures within the LGU. Ensuring meaningful public participation is essential for fostering ownership, legitimacy, and co-production in local market governance.

In terms of procurement and inclusion, consumers expressed moderate trust in LGU procurement systems, particularly those involving MSMEs, farmers, and women vendors. However, awareness of LGU sourcing programs, such as feeding initiatives and disaster kit procurement, remains low. This suggests that while the market has potential to strengthen inclusive local supply chains, current communication efforts and procurement transparency remain insufficient. The limited visibility of these initiatives prevents consumers from recognizing how local sourcing contributes to community welfare and economic empowerment.

These challenges collectively demonstrate the urgent need for a structured, evidence-based implementation plan that aligns physical infrastructure, management systems, and economic interventions. The implementation guidelines aim to translate the findings of this research into concrete policies, programs, and operational procedures that will enable the Gainza Public Market to function as a sustainable, inclusive, and community-driven local economic hub. By addressing the interrelated concerns of accessibility, activation readiness, procurement inclusiveness, and stakeholder collaboration, the LGU of Gainza can build a stronger foundation for local development and contribute to the broader goals of sustainable urban governance in Camarines Sur.

II. OBJECTIVES

To implement a comprehensive, inclusive, and sustainable operational framework for the Gainza Public Market within 12 months, improving infrastructure, governance, accessibility, and economic participation of local stakeholders.

Specific Objectives:

- a. To upgrade essential market facilities (water supply, drainage, lighting, sanitation, signage, and accessibility features) to at least 80% functionality within 6–12 months;
- b. To establish an operational market management system, including a Market Management Committee and updated market ordinance, within 4 months;
- c. To enhance vendor capacity through at least three training programs on financial management, marketing, sanitation, and customer service within 8 months;
- d. To operationalize the nearby transport terminal and improve market access routes within 10 months, increasing foot traffic by at least 30%;
- e. To increase consumer awareness and involvement through quarterly community consultations and regular updates, achieving at least 60% awareness level within 1 year; and,
- f. To institutionalize inclusive procurement practices, ensuring that at least 30% of LGU-sourced goods come from accredited MSMEs, farmers, or women vendors within 12 months.

III. STRATEGIC ACTION PLAN

The Action Plan outlines the concrete steps necessary to operationalize the sustainability strategies identified for the Gainza Public Market. It translates the study’s findings into time-bound, actionable interventions that address infrastructure gaps, strengthen governance mechanisms, and enhance stakeholder participation. By detailing specific activities, responsible persons, timelines, and expected outputs, the plan serves as a practical roadmap for transforming the market into a functional, inclusive, and sustainable hub for Camarines Sur.

Date / Timeline	Specific Actions	Person(s) Involved	Expected Output
Physical Infrastructure			
Month 1–2	Conduct full market facility audit (water, drainage, CR, lighting, signage, accessibility).	Municipal Engineering Office (MEO), Market Supervisor	Baseline assessment report
Month 3–6	Implement infrastructure repairs: water line installation, drainage upgrades, CR rehabilitation, lighting installation.	MEO, DPWH coordination	Improved facility functionality
Month 4	Install inclusive features: ramps, handrails, clear signages, designated PWD paths.	MEO, MSWDO	Accessible and inclusive market environment

Date / Timeline	Specific Actions	Person(s) Involved	Expected Output
Management Practices and Policies			
Month 2–3	Establish Market Management Committee (MMC) and draft updated Market Ordinance.	LGU, SB, Committee on Trade, Market Administrator	Functional MMC and draft ordinance
Month 4–6	Coordination with LGU transport office to operationalize terminal.	LGU Transport Office, Operators	Increased market accessibility
Economic Business Activities			
Month 4–7	Launch vendor capacity- building programs (financial literacy, digital marketing, sanitation compliance).	PESO, DTI, DA	Enhanced vendor skills
Quarterly	Conduct community consultations, dissemination drives, and consumer feedback surveys.	PIO, LGU	Higher stakeholder engagement
Sustainability Maps			
Month 5–9	Implement e-market integration: digital product listings, price updates, promotions.	ICT Office, PIO	Increased digital visibility
Month 6–12	Roll out inclusive procurement program and vendor accreditation system.	BAC, MSWDO, DTI	Transparent and equitable procurement
Continuous	Monitoring of cleanliness, waste management, and environmental practices.	MENRO, Market Staff	Cleaner and greener market

IV. BUDGETARY REQUIREMENTS AND SOURCE

The successful implementation of the proposed sustainability interventions for the Gainza Public Market will require adequate and well-allocated financial resources to support infrastructure upgrades, institutional strengthening, and community-based programs. This section outlines the estimated budgetary requirements needed to operationalize the action plan, ensuring that each activity is realistically funded and aligned with the LGU's fiscal capacity. It also identifies potential funding sources, including local government appropriations, external grants, and partnerships, to guarantee that the market's transformation into a sustainable hub is both achievable and financially sustainable.

Component	Estimated Cost (PHP)	Funding Source

Facility Rehabilitation (water, drainage, lighting, CRs)	15,000,000.00	LGU Annual Investment Plan (AIP), Provincial Assistance
Accessibility Improvements (ramps, signages, PWD paths)	750,000.00	LGU General Fund, MSWDO accessibility budget
Terminal Operationalization & Transport Improvements	2,000,000.00	LGU Transport Fund, Provincial Transport Office
Digitalization (e-market platform, digital board, marketing)	300,000.00	ICT Fund, DICT support
Vendor Training & Support Programs	250,000.00	DTI Negosyo Center, PESO Training Fund
Procurement & Accreditation System	450,000.00	LGU Procurement Office
Waste Management & Environmental Improvements	1,000,000.00	MENRO, DENR partnership
Monitoring & Evaluation	500,000.00	LGU M&E Fund
Estimated Total Budget	PHP 20,250,000.00	

Possible Additional Sources: DTI Livelihood Seeding Program, DA KADIWA Funds, DICT Digitalization Grants, NGO partnerships.

V. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) will be conducted to ensure that the implementation strategies align with the sustainability goals of the Gainza Public Market. The Market Management Committee will lead monthly monitoring of infrastructure, vendor compliance, sanitation, procurement processes, and consumer satisfaction. Quarterly evaluation reports will measure progress using performance indicators such as facility readiness, foot traffic count, vendor participation rate, procurement inclusiveness, and consumer feedback scores. Mid-year and end-year assessments will determine whether the SMART objectives are met and identify areas needing corrective action. The LGU will also utilize participatory M&E tools such as public scorecards, feedback kiosks, and stakeholder consultations. Results of monitoring activities will be documented and presented to the Municipal Mayor and Sangguniang Bayan to guide policy adjustments, budget allocations, and continuous improvement toward long-term sustainability.

CONCLUSIONS

This section presents the conclusions derived from the analysis of data and the synthesis of findings concerning the Gainza Public Market. The conclusions are structured to provide a definitive response to each of the study's research objectives, evaluating the current operational state, the potential for expansion, and the existing levels of sustainability within the facility. By distilling the complex interactions between institutional readiness and stakeholder experiences, this section serves as a reflective summary that highlights the critical gaps and strengths identified throughout the research. Each item below corresponds directly to a specific objective, offering a logical progression from the current status of the market toward the strategic guidelines necessary for its transformation into a sustainable community hub.

I. Current status of operation of the Gainza Public Market in terms of (a) physical infrastructure; (b) management practices; and, (c) economics and business activities.

This objective presented an assessment of the current operational status of the Gainza Public Market with respect to three major dimensions: physical infrastructure, management practices, and economic and business activities. Using the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model, the objective draws from stakeholder-generated data (Input), evaluates them through quantitative analysis and thematic interpretation (Process), and presents synthesized findings, conclusions, and recommendations (Output). By examining the interactions between structural conditions, governance performance, and economic viability, this established a comprehensive baseline that informs the development of strategic interventions necessary for the sustainable revitalization of the public market.

a. Physical Infrastructure

The Gainza Public Market is currently not structurally prepared for full-scale sustainable operation. The physical environment remains inadequate, specifically in the critical areas of sanitation, basic utilities, and safety systems. These deficiencies demonstrate that the market does not yet meet the minimum required standards for public health, physical accessibility, and structural resilience. While vendors perceive individual stall conditions as generally fair, the overall institutional assessment reveals that these infrastructure weaknesses serve as a primary barrier to establishing a reliable and sustainable economic hub.

b. Management Practices

The management systems of the Gainza Public Market are currently the most critical barrier to its sustainable operation. The research indicates that the Local Government Unit identifies governance as "very poor," characterized by significant deficiencies in transparency, accountability, and administrative responsiveness. While vendors perceive management as "fair," their confidence is undermined by financial constraints and a lack of clear enforcement protocols. This gap between institutional planning and ground-level execution suggests that without systemic management reforms, the market cannot yet function as a reliable or sustainable economic hub.

c. Economics and Business Practices

The Gainza Public Market is currently not functioning as an economically viable local commercial hub. While vendors indicate a willingness to participate and perceive a degree of feasibility due to affordable fees, the broader institutional assessment reveals that the market suffers from very weak competitiveness and insufficient demand drivers. The low level of vendor participation and limited diversity of goods suggest that consumers do not yet perceive the market as a primary destination, causing a cycle of low foot traffic and reduced economic dynamism. Consequently, structural and demand-related challenges are currently undermining the market's ability to stimulate local enterprise or contribute meaningfully to the municipality's economic growth.

II. Prospects for possible full operation of the Gainza Public Market in terms of (a) economic growth potential; (b) environmental sustainability; and, (c) policy and institutional readiness.

This research objective examined the prospects for the full operation of the Gainza Public Market by assessing its potential across three key dimensions: economic growth, environmental sustainability, and policy and institutional readiness. Using stakeholder responses from the LGU and vendors as the primary input, the study evaluated these dimensions through weighted mean analysis and thematic interpretation. The purpose of this objective is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how these factors interact to shape the market's viability as a sustainable hub. Guided by the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model, this section presents the data used (input), the analytical procedures employed (process), and the core findings, conclusions, and recommendations (output).

a. Economic Growth Potential

The Gainza Public Market holds substantial potential for successful full operation and local economic expansion, though this potential is currently characterized by a disparity in stakeholder confidence. While the Local Government Unit (LGU) maintains strong optimism regarding the market's capacity for revenue generation and support for local producers, vendor confidence remains moderate and has yet to fully align with these institutional expectations. This suggests that while structural and locational factors favor economic growth, perceived risks and past operational challenges continue to influence the caution shown by potential vendors. Ultimately, the market's future as an economic driver depends on bridging these perception gaps and translating high-level institutional planning into tangible incentives that foster vendor trust and participation.

b. Environmental Sustainability

The prospects for environmental sustainability at the Gainza Public Market are characterized by a strong institutional vision that has yet to be fully realized at the stakeholder level. The Local Government Unit (LGU) demonstrates a high level of readiness and willingness to invest in "green" systems, specifically in the areas of eco-friendly waste management and green infrastructure. However, a significant disparity exists in perceptions, as vendors and consumers provide only "fair" or "neutral" ratings regarding these initiatives. This suggests that while foundational policy structures for sustainability exist, institutional planning has not been effectively translated into visible, tangible interventions or active community engagement. Consequently, the market's potential as a "green" model remains theoretical until behavioral and market-based changes are integrated into daily operations.

c. Policy and Institutional Readiness

The research concludes that there is a robust foundation for the sustainable operation of the Gainza Public Market due to high levels of institutional readiness and policy alignment within the Local Government Unit (LGU). The LGU demonstrates very high confidence in its administrative capacity, existing ordinance support, and the alignment of the market project with broader municipal development plans. These findings suggest that the governance structures and organizational capacity are functioning cohesively, providing a strong enabling environment for the implementation of future sustainability initiatives. Ultimately, the high degree of institutional preparation indicates that the LGU is not only administratively ready but also organizationally equipped to manage and sustain long-term market operations.

III. Level of sustainability of Gainza Public Market in terms of (a) economic performance; (b) social inclusiveness; and (c) environmental management.

This objective evaluated the overall level of sustainability of the Gainza Public Market by examining three interrelated dimensions: economic performance, social inclusiveness, and environmental management. The purpose of this objective was to determine how well the market aligns with sustainable development standards and to assess its readiness to operate as a long-term, community-centered economic hub. Using the Input–Process–Output (IPO) model, the chapter summarizes the data gathered from the LGU, vendors, stallholders, and consumers (Input), applies descriptive statistical analysis and thematic interpretation (Process), and presents the synthesized findings, conclusions, and recommendations (Output). Together, these components provided a comprehensive understanding of the market’s sustainability status and guide future development strategies.

a. Economic Performance

The economic performance of the Gainza Public Market is currently classified as unsustainable, characterized by a significant disconnect between consumer behavior and the facility's economic goals. While consumers demonstrate a high level of awareness regarding the value of local markets and express strong support for "visible" sustainability initiatives like eco-friendly packaging, this awareness has not translated into stable patronage or a willingness to absorb higher costs associated with sustainable practices. The market’s inability to drive transformative consumer behavior suggests that its current economic model remains fragile, hampered by practical stakeholder considerations such as price sensitivity and convenience. Consequently, the market is not yet achieving the economic dynamism required to ensure long-term livelihood stability for vendors or consistent revenue generation for the municipality.

b. Social Inclusiveness

The research concludes that the Gainza Public Market has made significant progress in promoting social inclusivity through program-based initiatives, but it remains hampered by critical infrastructural and institutional gaps. While there is a strong foundation for social sustainability—particularly through active vendor support programs that empower vulnerable groups—the market is currently rated as "unsustainable" regarding gender-sensitive facilities. This disparity suggests that social responsibility is being treated as a series of isolated initiatives rather than a holistically integrated system. Consequently, while the market serves as a platform for social empowerment, the lack of inclusive infrastructure (such as specialized facilities for women and diverse groups) acts as a persistent barrier to achieving full social sustainability and equitable access for all community members.

c. Environmental Management

The environmental management of the Gainza Public Market is currently at a moderate level of sustainability, characterized by strong foundational waste management practices but significant vulnerabilities in long-term resilience. The research concludes that the Local Government Unit (LGU) has successfully prioritized "visible" environmental actions, such as waste reduction and recycling practices, which are actively supported by consumers due to their ease of implementation. However, the study identifies a critical gap in

climate change adaptation and disaster resilience, which ranked lowest among environmental indicators. This indicates that while the market is making progress toward immediate ecological protection, it remains structurally and operationally unprepared for long-term climatic shocks, suggesting that environmental sustainability is currently present but not yet fully optimized or resilient.

OBJECTIVE NO. 4 To develop an Implementation Guidelines for Gainza Public Market as a sustainable hub in Camarines Sur.

The development of Implementation Guidelines for the Gainza Public Market is a critical and essential step toward ensuring that the facility's revitalization is strategic, inclusive, and evidence-based. The research concludes that these guidelines are necessary to bridge the current operational gaps across economic, environmental, and institutional dimensions. By providing a structured framework, the guidelines serve as the primary mechanism for aligning diverse policies and stakeholder actions toward a common vision of sustainability. Ultimately, these guidelines act as a strategic roadmap that translates assessment data into concrete, locally adaptable actions, ensuring that the market's transformation into a sustainable hub is both manageable and resilient.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to provide a strategic framework for the revitalization of the Gainza Public Market. These recommendations are designed to translate the research data into actionable interventions that address identified gaps in infrastructure, governance, and economic performance. By offering a multi-dimensional approach covering physical improvements, policy reforms, and community engagement these suggestions aim to support the Local Government Unit (LGU) and its stakeholders in fostering a more resilient, inclusive, and environmentally responsible community hub. The following strategies are categorized to align with the study's specific objectives, ensuring a logical transition from academic assessment to practical, sustainable implementation.

I. On the Current Operational Status

a. Physical Infrastructure

It is recommended that the LGU prioritize the immediate rehabilitation of core utilities, specifically water, sanitation, and fire safety systems. These upgrades should be designed to meet or exceed national public health standards to ensure user safety. A phased engineering plan should be adopted to allow for improvements without completely displacing current vendors. This structural foundation is the first step in restoring the market's credibility as a public service facility.

b. Management Practices

The municipality should transition toward a digital governance model by implementing automated systems for fee collection and grievance reporting. This modernization should be supported by a clear, written manual of operations that defines the roles and responsibilities of all

market personnel. By reducing human error and increasing transparency, the LGU can foster a more professional and trustworthy administrative environment. Such reforms are necessary to attract serious investors and established traders.

c. Economics and Business Activities

To stimulate immediate activity, the LGU should introduce "pioneer incentives" such as graduated rental rates or tax holidays for the first year of operation. These incentives are specifically designed to attract a diverse set of vendors and increase the variety of goods available to consumers. By lowering the barrier to entry, the market can rapidly increase its occupancy and foot traffic. A more vibrant and diverse marketplace will naturally improve its overall competitiveness in the region.

II. On Prospects for Full Operation and Economic Expansion

a. Economic Growth Potential

The LGU should launch a comprehensive "Market Re-activation Campaign" that targets both local producers and the general buying public. This campaign must highlight new security features, improved safety standards, and the benefits of supporting local trade. By actively communicating these improvements, the LGU can bridge the existing confidence gap and encourage stakeholders to invest their time and resources. Consistent public engagement will be the key to shifting the market's current neutral perception to a positive one.

b. Environmental Sustainability

To bridge the gap between institutional planning and community practice the LGU should prioritize a formal roadmap that integrates waste segregation systems, renewable energy options (such as solar lighting), and green building features into the market's physical redevelopment. Focus on high-impact, visible practices that do not require financial sacrifice from stakeholders—such as the mandatory use of eco-friendly packaging—to build consumer awareness and support. Implement education and motivation programs for vendors and consumers to align their behavior with the LGU's sustainability goals, moving beyond "neutral" perceptions toward active participation. Establish practical systems for waste reduction, such as composting initiatives for organic market waste, to ensure resource efficiency and minimize the facility's environmental footprint.

c. Policy and Institutional Readiness

A permanent Market Sustainability Committee should be established within the LGU to provide multi-sectoral oversight. This committee would be responsible for ensuring that all market activities remain aligned with the municipality's long-term sustainability and development goals. By involving representatives from the environment, health, and economic departments, the LGU can ensure a balanced approach to market management. Regular oversight will prevent the recurrence of the management gaps identified in this study.

III. Level of Sustainability

a. Economic Performance

To transition the market toward a sustainable level of economic performance, the following strategies are recommended:

- a. Focus on low-cost, highly visible sustainability practices—such as waste-reduction incentives or localized "green" branding—to capitalize on existing consumer awareness and build market identity without imposing financial burdens.
- b. Develop motivation and education programs that move beyond general awareness, using specific incentives (e.g., loyalty rewards or promotional events) to encourage residents to shift their purchasing habits from neighboring towns to the Gainza market.
- c. Conduct a thorough review of fee structures and pricing to ensure they remain inclusive and reflect the economic reality of the local community, thereby addressing the current caution consumers feel regarding the financial costs of market participation.
- d. Establish a regular economic "sustainability rating" system to track vendor income stability, business viability, and consumer flow, allowing for data-driven adjustments to the market's operational guidelines.

b. Social Inclusiveness

The LGU should undergo a "Universal Design" retrofit to ensure the market is physically accessible to PWDs and senior citizens. This includes the installation of breastfeeding stations, gender-neutral restrooms, and improved lighting in all common areas. Beyond physical changes, the LGU should continue to protect the rights of vulnerable traders through equitable stall distribution policies. Making the market a safe and welcoming space for all will enhance its social value to the community.

c. Environmental Management

The market should operationalize a circular economy model by integrating on-site composting for organic waste and installing solar-powered lighting. These "green" features serve a dual purpose of reducing the facility's carbon footprint and lowering long-term utility costs. Additionally, mandatory waste segregation should be enforced through a rewards-based system for vendors who comply. This shift toward resource efficiency will set a benchmark for other public facilities in the province.

IV. Implementation Guidelines

The proposed Implementation Guidelines should be formally adopted through a municipal ordinance to ensure they have the necessary legal and budgetary backing. This ordinance will provide the institutional mandate required for long-term execution and staff accountability. Furthermore, the LGU should implement a quarterly "Sustainability Audit" to track progress against the indicators identified in the guidelines. This data-driven approach will allow the management to make real-time adjustments and ensure the project remains on track.

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